

1 **SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION**

2 **SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE 1: Comparison of accuracy and precision for machine**
 3 **learning and maximum likelihood estimation techniques for constant-rate Birth Death**
 4 **model.**

Parameters	Mean Absolute Error				Mean Relative Error			
	MLE	FFNN- Sumstats	CNN- CDV	FFNN- CDV	MLE	FFNN- Sumstats	CNN- CDV	FFNN- CDV
Speciation rate	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.14
Extinction rate	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.51	0.62	0.62	1.18
Net diversification rate	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.17
Turnover rate	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.12	0.40	0.48	0.50	0.88
Parameters	Pearson Correlation Coefficient				Bias			
	MLE	FFNN- Sumstats	CNN- CDV	FFNN- CDV	MLE	FFNN- Sumstats	CNN- CDV	FFNN- CDV
Speciation rate	0.97	0.98	0.97	0.93	0.008	0.005	0.005	0.003
Extinction rate	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.78	0.010	0.007	0.008	0.006
Net diversification rate	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.98	-0.002	-0.003	-0.002	-0.005
Turnover rate	0.92	0.95	0.94	0.82	0.0008	0.013	0.019	0.015

13 *For each estimated parameter and estimation method, we evaluated the accuracy on 500 test*
 14 *simulations in terms of: 1] Mean Absolute Error (MAE) in green, 2] Mean Relative Error (MRE)*
 15 *in blue, 3] Pearson correlation coefficient in yellow and 4] Bias in grey. The compared*
 16 *estimation methods are a) Maximum likelihood estimation MLE-based method, b) Feed-Forward*
 17 *Neural Network trained on summary statistics (FFNN-SS), c) Convolutional Neural Network*
 18 *trained on the CDV representation (CNN-CDV), d) FFNN trained on the CDV representation*
 19 *(FFNN-CDV). The MRE for turnover was very high with each method, which is partially due to*
 20 *the covered parameter space (uniformly covered between 0.01 and 1). The CNN-CDV exhibits a*
 21 *higher bias for the turnover rate.*

22 **SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE 2: Comparison of accuracy and precision for machine**
 23 **learning and maximum likelihood estimation techniques for Binary State Speciation and**
 24 **Extinction model.**

Parameters	Mean Absolute Error					Mean Relative Error				
	castor	diversitree	CNN- CDV	CNN- CDV-less	FFNN- CDV	castor	diversitree	CNN- CDV	CNN- CDV-less	FFNN- CDV
Speciation rate 1	0.076	0.048	0.047	0.150	0.084	0.16	0.10	0.10	0.31	0.17
Speciation rate 2	0.086	0.055	0.058	0.110	0.085	0.42	0.22	0.24	0.42	0.38
Extinction rate 1	0.097	0.064	0.058	0.146	0.109	3.15	1.65	1.80	4.58	4.08
Extinction rate 2	0.116	0.079	0.041	0.089	0.067	12.38	3.06	1.94	4.44	4.27
Transition rate	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.010	0.008	0.21	0.21	0.19	0.46	0.36
Parameters	Pearson Correlation Coefficient					Bias				
	castor	diversitree	CNN- CDV	CNN- CDV-less	FFNN- CDV	castor	diversitree	CNN- CDV	CNN- CDV-less	FFNN- CDV
Speciation rate 1	0.77	0.97	0.97	0.74	0.92	0.038	0.017	5e-04	0.003	6e-04
Speciation rate 2	0.67	0.93	0.92	0.75	0.84	0.045	0.012	-0.010	-0.013	-0.016
Extinction rate 1	0.65	0.92	0.92	0.48	0.73	0.040	0.016	-0.002	1e-04	0.009
Extinction rate 2	0.44	0.74	0.91	0.57	0.78	0.083	0.042	-0.006	-0.003	-0.003
Transition rate	0.94	0.94	0.95	0.71	0.85	5e-04	5e-04	-8e-04	8e-04	-4e-04

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 26 *For each estimated parameter and estimation method, we evaluated the accuracy on 9.983 test*
 27 *simulations in terms of: 1] Mean Absolute Error (MAE) in green, 2] Mean Relative Error (MRE)*
 28 *in blue, 3] Pearson correlation coefficient in yellow and 4] Bias in grey. The compared*
 29 *estimation methods are a) Maximum likelihood estimation MLE-based method using the R*
 30 *package castor, b) MLE-based method using the R package diversitree, c) Convolutional Neural*
 31 *Network trained on the CDV representation (CNN-CDV), d) CNN trained on CDV-less without*
 32 *individual information on tip state (CNN-CDV-less) and e) Feed-Forward Neural Network*
 33 *trained on the CDV representation (FFNN-CDV). The MRE for the turnover rate was very high*

- 34 *for each method, which is partially due to the covered parameter space (uniformly covered*
- 35 *between 0 and 1). With CNN-CDV, we obtain comparable results as with castor and diversitree.*

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37 **SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 1: Predicted versus target plots.**

38 For each parameter predicted for BD we show a plot of predicted versus target values for 500
 39 simulations from the test set, each dot representing one prediction: a) speciation rate λ , b)
 40 extinction rate μ , c) net diversification rate r , d) turnover rate ϵ . The dashed line represents the
 41 identity line, while the full line is the local polynomial regression with its 95% confidence
 42 interval delimited by the dotted lines.

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44 **SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 2 : Predicted versus target plots.**

45 For each parameter predicted for BiSSE we show a plot of predicted versus target values for
 46 9,983 simulations from the test set, each dot representing one prediction: a) speciation rate 1 λ_1 ,
 47 b) speciation rate 2 λ_2 , c) extinction rate 1 μ_1 , d) extinction rate 2 μ_2 , e) the transition rates
 48 $q_{12}=q_{21}$. The dashed line represents the identity line, while the full line is the local polynomial
 49 regression with its 95% confidence interval delimited by the dotted lines.

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51 **SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 3 : *Relative accuracy of CNN-CDV increases with the tree***
 52 ***size.***

53 *For each model a) constant-rate BD, and b) BiSSE, we display the quantile regression on the*
 54 *relative absolute error in solid line for each parameter as a function of tree size for 500 test trees*
 55 *(for BiSSE, 500 values are shown instead of 10.000 for visualization purposes). The area around*
 56 *the solid line delimited by the dotted lines represent the 95% confidence interval around the*
 57 *quantile regression.*